

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF BIOANALYTICAL UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF CARVEDILOL AND DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF CARVEDILOL IN BULK DRUG AND FORMULATION

A. L. Ware^{1,2*}, S.S. Pekamwar³

¹Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Hyderabad.

²Sanjivani College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Kopargaon.

³Swami Ramanand Tirth Marathwada University, Nanded.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 25/12/2020

Available online

31/01/2021

Keywords

Carvedilol,

UV-Spectrophotometric.

ABSTRACT

This Bioanalytical UV-spectrophotometric technique is quite simple, accurate, precise, reproducible, and sensitive. This bioanalytical method for determination of carvedilol. This UV-spectrophotometric method has been used for quantification of Carvedilol in tablet formulation also. The validation procedure confirms that this is an appropriate method for their quantification in the plasma and formulation. It is also used in routine quality control of the formulations containing this entire compound. In spectrum Carvedilol showed absorbance maximum at 289 nm. Validation parameters like linearity was found from 5-30 µg/ml accuracy was found to be 99.68%, precision was found to be within limit of 98% to 102%. For Ruggedness % RSD was also found less than 2 %.

Corresponding author

A. L. Ware

Sanjivani College of Pharmaceutical Education,
and Research, Kopargaon, At- Sahajanandnagar
Post- Shinganapur Tal- Kopargaon Dist- Ahmednagar
agastiware@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **A. L. Ware et al. A Review on Importance of Clinical Pharmacy Services in Oncology Care Centre. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2021:11(01).**

Copy right © 2021 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

www.iajpr.com

INTRODUCTION^[1]

The variation of the colour of a system with change in concentration of some component forms the basis of what the chemist commonly terms colorimetric analysis. The colour is usually due to the formation of a coloured compound by the addition of an appropriate reagent, or it may be inherent in the desired constituent itself. The intensity of the colour may then be compared with that obtained by treating a known amount of the substance in the same manner. Colorimetry is concerned with the determination of the concentration of a substance by measurement of the relative absorption of light with respect to a known concentration of the substance. In visual colorimetry, natural or artificial white light is generally used as a light source, and determinations are usually made with a simple instrument termed a colorimeter, or colour comparator. When the eye is replaced by a photoelectric cell (thus largely eliminating the errors due to the personal characteristics of each observer) the instrument is termed a photoelectric colorimeter. The latter is usually employed with light contained within a comparatively narrow range of wavelengths furnished by passing white light through filters, i.e. materials in the form of plates of coloured glass, gelatin, etc., transmitting only a limited spectral region: the name 'filter photometer' is sometimes applied to such an instrument.

In spectrophotometric analysis a source of radiation is used that extends into the ultraviolet region of the spectrum. From this, definite wavelengths of radiation are chosen possessing a bandwidth of less than 1 nm. This process necessitates the use of a more complicated and consequently more expensive instrument. The instrument employed for this purpose is a spectrophotometer. An optical spectrometer is an instrument possessing an optical system which can produce dispersion of incident electromagnetic radiation, and with which measurements can be made of the quantity of transmitted radiation at selected wavelengths of the spectral range. A photometer is a device for measuring the intensity of transmitted radiation or a function of this quantity. When combined in the spectrophotometer the spectrometer and photometer are employed conjointly to produce a signal corresponding to the difference between the transmitted radiation of a reference material and that of a sample at selected wavelengths. The chief advantage of colorimetric and spectrophotometric methods is that they provide a simple means for determining minute quantities of substances. The upper limit of colorimetric methods is, in general, the determination of constituents which are present in quantities of less than 1 or 2 per cent.

The sensitivity can, however, be improved if the technique of derivative spectrophotometry is employed. The development of inexpensive photoelectric colorimeters has placed this branch of instrumental chemical analysis within the means of even the smallest teaching institution. In this chapter we are concerned with analytical methods that are based upon the absorption of electromagnetic radiation. Light consists of radiation to which the human eye is sensitive, waves of different wavelengths giving rise to light of different colours, while a mixture of light of these wavelengths constitutes white light. White light covers the entire visible spectrum 400-760 nm. The approximate wavelength ranges of colours are given in Table No.1. The visual perception of colour arises from the selective absorption of certain wavelengths of incident light by the coloured object. The other wavelengths are either reflected or transmitted, according to the nature of the object, and are perceived by the eye as the colour of the object. If a solid opaque object appears white, all wavelengths are reflected equally; if the object appears black, very little light of any wavelength is reflected; if it appears blue, the wavelengths that give the blue stimulus are reflected, etc.

Table No.1 Approximate wavelengths of colours.

Ultraviolet	<400nm	Yellow	570-590nm
Violet	400-450nm	Orange	590-620nm
Blue	450-500nm	Red	620-760nm
Green	500-570nm	Infrared	>760nm

Present work aims at developing simple, precise, accurate Bioanalytical method for determination of carvedilol and use that method for determination of carvedilol in bulk drug and formulation.^[2-8]

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Material

Carvedilol was a gift sample from Dr. Reddys Lab, Hyderabad. All chemicals (distilled water, methanol) and reagents used were of analytical grade and purchased from Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India.

Apparatus

A Labindia UV-visible spectrophotometer (UV-T60-India) was used for all absorbance measurements with matched quartz cells.

Methodology

Method Development

Preparation of standard stock solution

Preparation of standard stock solution

10 mg Amount of standard was mixed with 10 ml acetonitrile to +2ml of rat plasma (untreated) then vertically shaken for 30 min then centrifuged at 5000rpm for 1 hr. Then it was filtered using membrane filters to get clear organic solution. Then it was filled in to the sample vials of HPLC and loaded on to HPLC for Run.

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Carvedilol was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in 20 ml distilled water by shaking manually for 10 min. The volume was adjusted with the same up to the mark to give the final strength, i.e. 100 µg/ml.

Selection of wavelength for analysis of Carvedilol

Appropriate volume 0.5 ml of standard stock solution of Carvedilol was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask, diluted to a mark with distilled water to give concentration of 5 µg/ml (and also 10, 15 µg/ml). The resulting solution was scanned in the UV range (200–400 nm). In spectrum Carvedilol showed absorbance maximum at 289 nm.

Validation of analytical method^[9]

The method was validated in terms of linearity, accuracy, precision, and ruggedness.

Linearity study

Different aliquots of Carvedilol in the range 0.5–3 ml were transferred into series of 10 ml volumetric flasks, and the volume was made up to the mark with distilled water to get concentrations 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 µg/ml, respectively. The solutions were scanned on a spectrophotometer in the UV range 200–400 nm. The spectrum was recorded at 289 nm. The calibration plot was constructed as concentration vs. absorbance

Accuracy

To the preanalysed sample solutions, a known amount of standard stock solution was added at different levels, i.e. 50%, 100%, and 150%. The solutions were reanalyzed by the proposed method.

Precision

Precision of the method was studied as intraday and interday variations. Intraday precision was determined by analyzing the 10, 15 and 20 µg/ml of Carvedilol solutions for three times in the same day. Interday precision was determined by analyzing the 10, 15, and 20 µg/ml of Carvedilol solutions daily for 3 days over the period of week.

Sensitivity

The sensitivity of measurements of Carvedilol by the use of the proposed method was estimated in terms of the limit of quantification (LOQ) and limit of detection (LOD). The LOQ and LOD were calculated using equation $LOD = 3 \times N/B$ and $LOQ = 10 \times N/B$, where 'N' is standard deviation of the peak areas of the drugs ($n = 3$), taken as a measure of noise, and 'B' is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve.

Repeatability

Repeatability was determined by analyzing 20 µg/ml concentration of Carvedilol solution for six times.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness of the proposed method is determined for 20 µg/ml concentration of Carvedilol by analysis of aliquots from a homogenous slot by two analysts using same operational and environmental conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solubility study

Table.no. 2 Solubility studies:

Solvent	Solubility(mg/ml)
Ehanol	1.5
Methanol	0.9
Alcohol	1.2
Chloroform	1.5
Acetone	1.3
Distilled water	0.5

The pure API of Carvedilol is freely soluble in inorganic solvents and sparingly soluble in aqueous solutions

Selection of wavelength for analysis of Carvedilol

During the development phase, the use of ethanol as the diluent resulted in preferable outcome in UV analysis. The pre-determined wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{max}) was 289 nm.

Fig.no. 1 UV –visible spectrum.

Table no. 3 Results of selection of wavelength.

Stocks	Wavelength of stocks	Absorbance
5 µg/ml	289	0.357
10 µg/ml	289	0.596
15 µg/ml	289	0.915

METHOD VALIDATION

Linearity

Table no. 4 Results of Linearity.

Concentration (ug/ml)	Absorbance(nm)
0	0
5	0.142
10	0.273
15	0.404
20	0.532
25	0.659
30	0.791

Fig.no. 2 Results of Calibration graph.

Accuracy (recovery) data for Carvedilol

N=3

Fig .no.3 Accuracy 50%.

N=3

Fig.no.4 Accuracy 100%.

N=3

Fig. no.5 Accuracy 150%.

Table no. 5 Results of Accuracy.

%Concentration (at specification Level)N=3	absorbance	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	0.4215	2.4	2.499	99.93	99.68
100%	0.6412	5.0	4.990	99.08	
150%	0.9198	10	9.995	99.95	

Precision

Fig.no.6 Intra-day and inter-day precision determined for three different concentrations of Carvedilol ($n=3$).

Table no.6 Intra-day and inter-day precision determined for three different concentrations of Carvedilol ($n=3$).

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Intra-day precision			Inter-day precision		
	Absorbance measured	RSD (%)	Average (%)	Absorbance measured	RSD (%)	Average (%)
10	0.4125	0.130	98.97	0.4120	0.250	98.98
15	0.6146	0.095	98.60	0.7254	0.095	98.72
20	0.8210	0.125	98.78	0.8213	0.080	98.82

Sensitivity :

The linearity equation was found to be $Y = 0.263X + 0.0075$. The LOD and LOQ for Carvedilol were found to be $0.52 \mu\text{g}$ and $2.98 \mu\text{g}$, respectively.

Repeatability

Fig.no.7 Results of Repeatability.

Table.no. 7 Results of Repeatability.

Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance measured (Mean ± SD)	Amount Found (%)	RSD (%)
120	0.7410±0.0523	99.68	0.023

Repeatability was determined by analyzing 20 µg/ml concentration of Carvedilol solution for six times and the % amount found was 99.68 % RSD < 2.

Ruggedness

Fig.no.8 Results of Ruggedness.

The peak area was measured for same concentration solutions, six times. The results are in the acceptable range for both the drugs. The result showed that the % RSD was less than 2%.

Table no. 8 Results of Ruggedness.

Analyst	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance measured (Mean \pm SD)	Amount Found (%)	RSD (%)
I	20	0.7126 \pm 0.0016	99.97	0.03
II	20	0.7214 \pm 0.0012	99.13	0.02

CONCLUSION

This UV-spectrophotometric technique is quite simple, accurate, precise, reproducible, and sensitive. The UV method has been developed for quantification of Carvedilol in tablet formulation. The validation procedure confirms that this is an appropriate method for their quantification in the formulation. It is also used in routine quality control of the formulations containing this entire compound.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author gratefully acknowledges to my guide for the supporting of my work and review of the data Dr. Reddy's laboratory, Hyderabad for providing gift sample of carvedilol, Sanjivani College of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Kopergaon for providing necessary support and facilities.

REFERENCES

1. G.H.Jeffery,J.Bassett,J.Mendham,R.C.Denney, Textbook of quantitative chemical analysis, fifth edition, Published by John Wiley and Sons:645-646.
2. Bilal Yilmaz, and Sakir Arslan, Determination of Carvedilol in Human Plasma by Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry Method, Journal of Chromatographic Science, January 2011; Vol. 49:35-39.
3. Basaveswara rao M.V, Nagendrakumar A. V, New validated RP–HPLC method for the estimation of carvedilol in pharmaceutical formulation, International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 2012 ; Vol 4, Issue 2:353-358.
4. Ramesh Gannu,Vamshi Vishnu Yamsani &Prof. Yamsani Madhusudan Rao,New RP-HPLC method with UV-detection for the determination of carvedilol in human serum, Journal of Liquid Chromatography and Related Technologies, 2007; Volume 30, Issue11.
5. Abdullah , Waqas Jamil, Hira Shariq, Jawaid Ahmed Siddiqui, IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences (IOSR-JPBS), e-ISSN:2278-3008, p-ISSN:2319-7676. (Nov. - Dec.2016); Volume 11, Issue 6 Ver.II: 93-97.
6. Soo-Hwan Kim, Sang Hun Lee, Hye Jung Lee, American Journal of Analytical Chemistry, 2010; 1: 135-143.
7. Rajan V. Rele , Prathamesh P. Tiwatane, UV Spectrophotometric estimation of Carvedilol Hydrochloride by second order derivative methods in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form, Research J. Pharm. and Tech. Dec. 2014; 7(12): 1459-1462.
8. Rajeshwari Rathod , L Poorna Chandra Prasad, Shubha Rani, Manish Nivsarkar, Harish Padh, J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci 2007; Oct 1 857(2):219-223.
9. ICH: Q2B, Analytical Validation – Methodology (1996).

54878478451201207

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

